

ENHANCING LECTURER TEACHING COMPETENCE IN CDIO VIA WORKPLACE LEARNING

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Abstract

This paper shares how the Course Management Team of the Diploma in Chemical Engineering of Singapore Polytechnic uses workplace learning based on the 70:20:10 Model of Learning and Development to develop the teaching competency of its lecturers based on the CDIO Framework to deliver its new spiral curriculum course structure. The aim of the spiral curriculum is to enhance student learning and retention of core chemical engineering knowledge, laboratory skills, and skills process operations (i.e. skills in operating chemical plants). This paper first briefly outlines what is meant by workplace learning, and explains why it is important for lecturers in today's context. It then shares the unique features of our spiral curriculum, namely in terms of using "cross-cutting" modules that integrate with core modules taught using "block teaching" approach. This creates a unique learning needs for the teaching team, because such a course structure requires that more lecturers to be well-versed in teaching more modules in a more intensive manner. This is a stark departure from earlier teaching arrangement whereby one lecturer teaches only 2 or 3 modules. There is thus an urgent need to prepare our lecturers in a timely manner to support the new spiral curriculum course structure. The paper then presents the 70:20:10 Model as an approach that portrays a more realistic approach towards learning, whereby bulk of the learning actually took place in the course of carrying out various jobs at the workplace (about 70% of the time). This is followed by an introduction to the Adding, Embedding, Extracting Model (AEEM) to derive learning from work at each of the three stages. The paper shares the author's experience with AEEM and provides examples at each stage on how to develop lecturers' competency to teach the "cross-cutting" modules and/or core modules using "block teaching". This paper concludes with a discussion of main challenges faced and key learning points gained.

Keywords: *Workplace Learning, Spiral Curriculum, Teaching Competence, CDIO*

Introduction

The Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) course of Singapore Polytechnic (SP) adopted the CDIO framework (www.cdio.org) as the basis for its 3-year curriculum since 2007 to produce the next generation of engineers. The framework provides students with an education stressing engineering fundamental set in the context of Conceiving, Designing, Implementing, Operating real-world systems and products. More recently, we introduced a new course structure based on spiral curriculum (Bruner, 1960) that took effect from April 2018 for Semester 1, Academic Year 2018/2019 (Cheah & Yang, 2018). It is an approach to education that introduces key concepts to students at a young age and covers these concepts repeatedly, with increasing degrees of complexity. This approach is also known as a "spaced" or "distributed" approach. It contrasts with "blocked" or "massed" curricula, which do not introduce difficult concepts until the student has reached a higher level of education. The spiral curriculum course structure requires a new way to teaching where lecturers need to be more well-versed in several disciplines and also work closely with other lecturers. This is important to ensure that topics to be learnt are sequenced in a progressive manner, so that modules within the same semester of study can mutually support one another, and modules at later semesters build on modules from earlier semesters.

Standard 10 of the CDIO Framework, "Enhancement of Faculty Teaching Competence" states the following:

"A CDIO program provides support for faculty to improve their competence in integrated learning experiences (Standard 7), active and experiential learning (Standard 8), and assessing student learning (Standard 11). The nature and scope of faculty development practices will vary with programs and institutions. Examples of actions that enhance faculty competence include support for faculty participation in university and external faculty development programs, forums for sharing ideas and best practices, and emphasis in performance reviews and hiring on effective teaching methods."

This paper shows how workplace learning is used to provide continuing professional development to our team of lecturers to better prepare them to tackle the challenges brought about by the implementation of the spiral curriculum.

What is Workplace Learning?

Lee, et al (2004) charged that there is no singular definition or one unified approach to what “workplace learning” is, what it should be, or who it is/should be for. Bratton, et al (2008) noted that the term workplace learning has become an established metaphor for capturing formal, non-formal, self-directed collective and even tacit informal learning activities. According to these authors, it is an interdisciplinary body of knowledge and theoretical inquiry that draws upon adult learning, management theory, industrial relations, sociological theory, etc. Two other commonly encountered words are: work-based learning, and work-integrated learning, which are sometimes used interchangeably with workplace learning. In Singapore’s context, the Institute of Adult Learning makes the following distinctions between workplace learning and work-based learning (IAL, 2016):

- Work-based Learning – prepares students for employment. Examples include internship and trainee arrangements, often undertaken in conjunction with classroom learning.
- Workplace Learning – develops employees through doing the work. This development leverages on learning that happens naturally in the workplace.

Our use of workplace learning is consistent with the definition provided by IAL. The next section explains the importance of workplace learning for lecturer.

Why Workplace Learning for Lecturer?

Like many companies, academic institutions are increasing turning towards workplace learning as a way forward in continuing to hone the teaching competency of its lecturers.

The challenges faced by academics in upgrading their knowledge and skills are somewhat different from the corporate world. Lecturers often find it difficult to take time-off (say, 2 to 3 days) to attend training programs during office hours, most notably because of clashes with teaching schedule, and the challenges of arranging for make-up classes, that has to match availability of faculty, students and classroom. On the other hand, school vacation (which is fixed by the academic calendar) does not offer much respite for lecturers either, as many are making use the time to catch up with a plethora of administrative work, module review, or serving as liaison officers for students who are on mandatory internship during the vacation. Lecturers are also reluctant to make use of school vacation to attend training programs, understandably because they want to use this time for family vacation or other short excursions.

SP therefore turned to workplace learning as a way to provide continuing professional development for its lecturers. This practice varies from school to school and from diploma to diploma, depending on each school’s organization and the diploma’s course structure. The next section briefly explains the course structure for DCHE and the special challenges in teaching that it presented.

The DCHE Spiral Curriculum Course Structure

The DCHE Spiral Curriculum Course Structure for was introduced in Semester 1, Academic Year 2018/2019 in April 2018I, starting with Year 1 students. A simplified representation for Year 1 and Year 2 is shown in Figure 1. A key feature of the spiral curriculum is the use of “block teaching” and “cross-cutting” modules.

DCHE Course	Cross-Cutting Module	Core DCHE Module	Core DCHE Module	Core DCHE Module	Other Module (Note 1)
Year 2 Sem 2 (Stage 2B)	<i>POS2</i>	<i>DCHE 2B-1</i>	<i>DCHE 2B-2</i>	<i>DCHE 2B-3</i>	Others
Year 2 Sem 1 (Stage 2A)	<i>POS1</i>	<i>DCHE 2A-1</i>	<i>DCHE 2A-2</i>	<i>DCHE 2A-3</i>	Others
Year 1 Sem 2 (Stage 1B)	<i>LPS2</i>	<i>DCHE 1B-1</i>	<i>DCHE 1B-2</i>	<i>DCHE 1B-3</i>	Others
Year 1 Sem 1 (Stage 1A)	<i>LPS1</i>	<i>DCHE 1A-1</i>	<i>DCHE 1A-2</i>	<i>DCHE 1A-3</i>	Others

Note 1: These include modules offered and supported by other (non-DCHE) diploma / school, e.g. chemistry, mathematic, etc.

Figure 1. DCHE Spiral Curriculum Course Structure

As can be seen in Figure 1, there are 4 “cross-cutting” modules, one for each semester, shown as *LPS1*, *LPS2*, *POS1* and *POS2*. A “cross-cutting” module, in the context of our spiral curriculum, is one that integrate topics covered in the other core modules and provide students with hands-on experience that require them to use knowledge gained from these core modules. The author is a member of the teaching team responsible for developing a new 45-hr “cross-cutting” module *Laboratory and Process Skills 2*, abbreviated as *LPS2* in Figure 1. The module is offered in Stage 1B (i.e. Year 1 Semester 1) and provides, in an integrative manner, the hands-on activities for topics covered in the 3 core modules (60-hour each) within the same semester, namely *Chemical Engineering Thermodynamics*, *Heat Transfer and Equipment*, and *Fluid Flow and Equipment*, shown as *DCHE 1B-1*, *DCHE 1B-2* and *DCHE 1B-3* as can be seen in Figure 1. These 3 modules are taught using the “block teaching” approach. Such coverage is consistent with the horizontal integration of CDIO Standard 3 Integrated Curriculum.

Figure 2 illustrate this for modules in Stage 1B (i.e. Year 1, Semester 2). The “cross-cutting” *LPS2* module is taught over the full semester (15 weeks) whereas the 3 core modules, i.e. *DCHE 1B-1*, *DCHE 1B-2* and *DCHE 1B-3* are delivered in shorter duration. As such, “block teaching” means a more “compact” teaching format. This means that a 45- or 60-hour module now needs to be completed within lesser weeks instead of over a full semester (15-weeks) which is traditionally the case. This necessarily means higher contact hours per week for the module. Other modules such as chemistry, mathematics, general education and stakeholder modules etc that are

serviced by other schools are not integrated and are delivered in the usual manner over the entire semester.

Stage 1B, Academic Year _____ : Week No.	1	Laboratory & Process Skills 2	Core DCHE1B-1			Other Modules
	2					
	3					
	4					
	5		Core DCHE1B-2			
	6					
	7		Core DCHE1B-3			
	8	Mid-Semester Test				
	9	Term Break				
	10					
	11					
	12	Laboratory & Process Skills 2	Core DCHE1B-1	Core DCHE1B-2	Core DCHE1B-3	Other Modules
	13					
	14					
	15					
	16					
	17					
	18					
	19	Semester Examination				
	20	Semester Examination				

Figure 2. Revised Course Structure for Stage 1B Chemical Engineering Spiral Curriculum

The sequencing of core modules for “block teaching” allows for better alignment with the various hands-on learning tasks covered in *LPS2*. This in turn leads to more effective student engagement and learning of key concepts, and development of desired skills and attitudes (CDIO Standard 7 - Integrated Learning Experiences and CDIO Standard 8 Active Learning) and student learning (CDO Standard 11 Learning Assessment).

Similar implementation of such “cross-cutting” modules and “block teaching” in other stages of study also enables the vertical integration of the curriculum. Such a course structure allows better delivery of learning outcomes based on the CDIO Framework. Using *LPS2* as an example, in terms of a fully integrated curriculum (CDIO Standard 3), it can be seen that *LPS2* is fully back-integrated with *LPS1* in Stage 1A, and also forward-integrated with *POSI* in Stage 2A. An example would be the integration of self-directed learning (SDL) skills in DCHE, which started with enhancing students’ growth mindset in *LPS1*, explicit teaching of SDL skills in *LPS2*, followed by applications in *POSI*, while at the same time students also master core skills in chemical processing technologies such as reading process flow diagram in *LPS1*, interpreting piping and instrumentation diagram

and line-tracing in *LPS2*, and writing standard operating procedures for plant operation in *POSI*.

Challenges in “Block Teaching”

One of the main challenges in implementing the spiral curriculum is the way teaching of modules will be carried out. The combined impact of “block teaching” and “cross-cutting” modules is that more lecturers are now required to be well-versed in teaching more modules in a more intensive manner. For example, a lecturer who had been teaching *DCHE 1B-1* in the past must now be acquainted with the topics in *DCHE 1B-2* and *DCHE 1B-3*, in order to be able to effectively facilitate student learnings in their learning tasks in *LPS2*; which contain elements of all 3 core modules. In addition, a lecturer must also be well-informed in how his/her module can leverage on student learning in earlier modules and also how his/her modules can support later modules.

This is in contrast with previous course structure whereby each lecturer tends to focus on teaching one or two modules only. These lecturers may only have academic knowledge about the topics they are now required to teach, acquired many years back during their university days. More importantly, many of our lecturers do not possess extensive working experience in chemical plant operations, and as such will have difficulty relating the topics in the spiral curriculum to real-world work situations. Such condition necessitates the training of lecturers in time for delivering the new spiral curriculum.

More importantly, due to the integrative nature of our integrated curriculum, it is highly unlikely that we can find an external training program that can meet the needs of our lecturers. Even if there is one such training, it is unlikely that the entire teaching team is able to attend such a training at the same time. The nature of training required is therefore best delivered in-house using own facilities in the laboratories. There is therefore a strong need to consider lecturers professional development via workplace learning, and the onus of delivering the required training thus fall on the shoulders of the module teaching team. This means we have to undertake

The 70:20:10 Model for Workplace Learning

Billet (2014) noted that over the past two decades, through interviews with workers from a range of occupations about how they learn through and for work, consistently they described it being premised upon: (i) engagement in work activities, (ii) observing and listening and (iii) “just being in the workplace”. Working is therefore highly intertwined with learning and consequently as in the words of Michael Fullan: “Learning is the Work” (Fullan, 2011). Learning at the workplace therefore mostly occurred through work-related interactions, where skills were upgraded, and knowledge is acquired and is generally described as contributing to the learning of both the individual employee and the organization as a whole (Cacciattolo, 2015).

The 70:20:10 Model is a learning and development model that arisen from the above observations. It stated that 70 percent of learning happens in the workplace through practice and on-the-job experiences; 20 percent comes through other people via coaching, feedback, and networking; and 10 percent is delivered through formal learning interventions. It is a model that is easy to understand but equally easy to misunderstand. The 70:20:10 concept makes intuitive sense, as most of what employees learn, they learn on-the-job during the course of doing their work - that is where they spend most of their time. Practical examples of 70:20:10 are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Practical Examples of 70:20:10

70 – Learn & Develop Through Experience
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply new learning in real situations • Use feedback to try a new approach to an old problem • New work and solving problems within role • Increased span of control • Increased decision making • Champion and/or manage changes • Cover for others on leave • Exposure to other departments/roles • Take part in project or working group • Coordinated role swaps or secondments • Stretch assignments • Interaction with senior management, e.g. meetings, presentations • Day-to-day research, web browsing • Leadership activities, e.g. lead a team, committee membership, executive directorships • Cross-functional introductions, site/customer visits • Research and apply best practice • Apply standards and processes, e.g. Six Sigma • Work with consultants or internal experts • Internal/external speaking engagements • Budgeting • Interviewing • Project reviews • Community activities and volunteering
20 – Learn & Develop Through Others
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informal feedback and work debriefs • Seeking advice, asking opinions, sounding out ideas • Coaching from manager/others • 360 feedback • Assessments with feedback • Structured mentoring and coaching • Learning through teams/networks • External networks/contacts • Professional/Industry association involvement or active membership • Facilitated group discussion, e.g. Action Learning
10 – Learn & Develop Through Structured Courses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Courses, workshops, seminars • eLearning • Professional qualifications/accreditation • Certification • Formal education, e.g. University, Business School

It is important to note that the numbers 70:20:10 merely served as a useful reminder that most learning occurs in the context of the workplace rather than in formal learning situations and that learning is highly context dependent. Despite the lack of empirical data supporting the 70:20:10 distribution, it nonetheless remains the most popular percentages widely quoted and used by many organizations. As noted by Arets, et al (2016), it is not about the fixed ratio, but rather it is all about the mix in learning approaches that can be designed to bring about change. Blackman et al (2016) who studied the model for its effectiveness as a model for middle management capability development in the Australian public sector, cautioned that it is important the elements in the 70:20:10 model should not be perceived to be implemented in isolation. Rather, an integrated and complementary approach must be adopted. In practice, the 70:20:10 model is often implemented using the Adding, Embedding, Extracting Model (AEEM) as will be explained next.

AEEM for Workplace Learning

The AEEM (Adding, Embedding, Extracting Model) for workplace learning (Figure 3) is a useful model that can be used for exploiting development opportunities in the workplace and making informal learning more effective (Jennings, 2014).

Implementation of workplace learning can be enhanced with the use of proper performance support (Arets, et al, 2016). Rossett & Schafer (2006) define performance support as “a helper in life and work” that provides “a repository for information, processes, and perspectives that inform and guide planning and action”. Performance support comes in many forms whether it is getting guidance via a checklist, common time slot for meetings, help desk, access to experts, etc.

Figure 3. The Adding, Embedding, Extracting Model (AEEM) for workplace learning

Workplace Learning in DCHE using 70:20:10 Model

The 70:20:10 Model had been introduced by the SP Management recently to build up staff capability using an Individual Development Plan (IDP) where each lecturer plans for his/her personal and professional development. Consistent with the institution-wide initiative, the DCHE Course Management Team (CMT) henceforth adopted the 70:20:10 Model to introduce workplace learning to

build up staff capability in delivering the spiral curriculum, in particular in the area of chemical process plant operation, brought about by the use of “cross-cutting modules” and “block teaching”. The DCHE Course Chair formed three curriculum development teams, one for each year of study led by one CMT member.

Learning is built into the curriculum development work using AEEM. Table 2 shows the work done in the three stages of the AEEM, using the “cross-cutting” module *LPS2* as an example.

Table 2. AEEM Examples of Work Done in *LPS2*

Adding learning to work	As members of the Year-1 Curriculum Development Team to rationalize, streamline, and sequence the content for “block teaching” in consultation with Senior Academic Mentor Time is set aside (Wednesday, 1 – 5 pm) during the developmental phase so that all involved do not have teaching duties during this period, hence can meet up for discussions
Embedding learning within workflows	Lecturer in charge of developing an activity prepare suggested lesson plan for the activity, model answers and sample calculations, along with brief guidance notes Lecturer in charge of developing an activity conduct a boot camp for the rest of the teaching team, at least 2 weeks before start of semester On-going consultation with lecturer developing content: Just-in-time clarification (e.g. calculations or result analysis), updates on errors previously not spotted
Extracting learning from work	Carry out regular updates among teaching team members via email, after every activity, on new learning if any, or insights Conduct After Action Review of entire module at the end of the semester, identify areas of improvement, prepare new performance support resources, if any Prepare facilitation notes based on teaching experience during the entire duration of pilot launch, to assist in the next run of the module

The entire teaching team for *LPS2* consists of 8 lecturers, whereby 5 lecturers (including the author) are full-time staff and 3 are adjunct lecturers. The author and two lecturers (one from the teaching team and also a CMT member) and another lecturer not from the teaching team took the lead for the development work for *LPS2*. The development of learning tasks was divided among these 3 team members based on each member’s domain knowledge. The rest of the full-time teaching members are themselves leading the changes in other modules for example *DCHE 1B-1* and *DCHE 1B-3*.

Altogether these 3 team members designed a total of 11 learning activities (using the CDIO Framework) for *LPS2*. Workplace learning takes the form of cross-training among the lecturers. The lecturer who developed an activity took the lead to provide proper performance support for the rest of the teaching team. The first author

for example, conducted a 3-hour boot camp for the three activities that he designed. To help the teaching team, he also drafted some brief guidance notes and prepared model answers for each activity. Similar performance support was provided for the remaining eight activities. On-going discussion was carried among team members even after the *LPS2* module was rolled out, where the learning activities were finetuned.

At the conclusion of the semester, an After-Action Review (AAR) of the module was carried out as part of the module review process. Items that worked and not worked were discussed; and areas of improvement identified. Finetuning of support measures were noted based on feedback from team members, and survey of students on their learning experience in the module.

Lastly, it is worth noting that student feedback indicated that students found the approach useful in helping them learn better, although some initial adjustments were needed in keeping up with the more intense contact (Yang, Cheah & Phua, 2021).

Reflections: Challenges and Learning Points

One of the key challenges in the development of the module is that of coordination. During the earlier phase of module development, numerous discussions were carried out to scope and sequence the activities. This was done in parallel with the planning of how the “block teaching” for the 3 core modules is to be done. The development team also had on-going discussions with other colleagues who had the relevant industry/academic experience for each of the activity being developed; and worked closely with module development teams for the 3 core modules in the same semester as well as module development teams for core modules in the past and subsequent semesters to ensure industry relevance, proper integration and the right level of progression. Scheduling these meetings become more challenging when the semester got going.

Another challenge is to keep all team members updated and abreast of the latest version of each activity. This is because not all development work were completed before the start of a semester. The 11 activities in *LPS2* were conducted once per week over a period of 13 weeks within a 15-week semester – one week is taken up for mid-semester test (MST) during which no classes are conducted, and one week for make-up class in the event of a public holiday (Figure 2). The module is delivered to 7 classes each week. Despite the best of intentions, and having cross-checked the design of each activity, not all mistakes were picked up before the start of the semester. As it turned out, several minor mistakes were discovered during the delivery of the module.

The teaching team may not have been fully prepared to deliver each activity exactly as intended. Simply put, the lecturer who designed an activity best knows exactly how it is to be delivered. However, he/she may not be able to share every single aspect or insight required for exact delivery during the boot camps. Indeed, some insights only came to us later, at the time of our own delivery of the very activity itself. Due to timetabling

constraints, the authors' own class is scheduled in the middle of the week. Hence, it is not always possible to share these insights in time with other teaching team members whose classes preceded our own.

Furthermore, to conduct numerous boot camps for a large teaching team presents its own challenges due to availability of all members, in particular adjunct lecturers. Lecturers who are full-time staff also had other work commitments. As a result, all boot camps had to be conducted twice, with the hope that all members can be briefed on what to do for each activity. Even then, several one-to-one sessions still had to be arranged for individuals who were unable to attend both sessions. There was also an instance where an adjunct lecturer pulled out at the last minute due to other commitments. All these translated to more time and effort, to ensure all members were sufficiently prepared to facilitate the learning process effectively.

Seen holistically, the most important benefit would be the professional development of the entire teaching team within office hours without incurring additional training cost. The cross-training benefits everyone, working collaboratively and growing professionally. Colleagues who had the relevant industry experience and/or technical know-how were able to develop as mentors, and to help ensure knowledge transfer to younger colleagues. The teaching team also learnt to step out of one's comfort zone and take on teaching of new module, of which some content could only be learnt "just-in-time" before they had to teach students. The other benefit gained was the enhanced understanding of the entire course structure and contents of all related modules in the preceding semester, current semester and subsequent semesters, which is helpful taking on the teaching of other modules.

Overall, team members expressed satisfaction with the on-the-job workplace learning that was put in place. The mutually supporting nature of our implementation of 70:20:10 model for workplace learning meant that every lecturer had a role to play in training fellow colleagues and in return be trained. Lecturers teaching some of the technical topics for the first time, in particular, reported the usefulness of the boot camp. Everyone also contributed positively to ways to improve the module in the future.

Conclusion

This paper presented an approach used to implement workplace learning for lecturers teaching the Diploma in Chemical Engineering based on the 70:20:10 Model. While many of activities described in this paper are not new, what is new here is the way professional development for lecturers can take place, at least for the team. The development work achieved via workplace learning through development of the new module and preparing colleagues for module delivery, we clearly see the benefit of shifting from formal training that takes place away from work to informal learning as part of work. The ultimate goal would be to use workplace learning and development to promote of a culture of

sharing among the lecturers, so as to further improve the teaching of chemical engineering using the spiral curriculum course structure.

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